

Impacts of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Dental Health of US Students

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused global lockdowns and social distancing, which have greatly changed people's life styles and overall health. We are interested to explore how this has affected adolescences' dental health. Our study used an online survey for US students aged 10-18 to examine the pandemic's impacts on eating habits, dental homecare, and dental visits. Wilcoxon two-sample and Chi-square tests were performed to compare the variables between students who kept routine dental checkups during the pandemic with those who did not. Using a logistic regression model, we also explored whether fear level of COVID-19 and family cultural background associate with dental visit decisions. We found that 54.7% of respondents have increased snack consumption due to the pandemic. About 19.1% have increased supplemental intake. Among all supplements, the major form was gummy (60.4%). For dental homecare, 21.0% reported less seriousness, and 64.7% reported the same level of seriousness. Routine dental visits during the pandemic have decreased. Students with greater fear levels and non-US cultural backgrounds tended not to visit the dentist during the pandemic compared to students with lower fear levels and US cultural backgrounds ($P_s < 0.01$). Our results suggest that the pandemic has had an overall negative impact on the dental health of US students, associated with

increased fear levels and a non-US cultural background. Dental care providers should be more proactive in providing dental health education and consider cultural backgrounds. Mental health counseling may also be helpful to maintain dental visits by minimizing fear levels.

Keywords

COVID-19, pandemic, dental health, eating habits, dental visit, fear and culture

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19, an infectious respiratory disease caused by the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, has since spread across many countries, with over 183 million confirmed cases and over 4 million confirmed deaths (Pettersson et al., 2021). As a result of the global COVID-19 pandemic, governments around the world have enforced safety precautions to minimize spread, including lockdowns and social distancing. The pandemic has forced many group activities, such as school and sports, to cancel. Many schools have shifted to either remote or hybrid instruction, or have closed. In fact, this past year, over 168 million students worldwide have almost missed a year of school (United Nations, 2021). As a result, students have had to spend prolonged periods of time indoors, resulting in lifestyle changes, including eating habits and dental hygiene, which would propose a change in dental caries risk (Chankanka O, et al, 2011).

Dental health is essential for the general health of adolescents. Routine dental visits allow teeth to be regularly cleaned and checked, helping to prevent and treat oral diseases timely. During the COVID-19 pandemic, many people have changed their perceptions and decisions toward dental visits, causing increased dental problems. In Turkey and China, non-emergency routine dental visits decreased drastically to 10-30% of those before the pandemic (Guo et al.,

2020; Üstün et al., 2021). A major Swiss dental care center recorded 3109 emergency dental visits and noted a significant increase in patients with dental abscesses during lockdown (Eggmann et al., 2021). The pandemic and COVID-19 have led to the development of fear and/or insecurity, which suggests fewer dental visits (Heiat et al., 2021). In a survey of 1003 parents in Brazil, 51 reported that their child had dental trauma during the pandemic (Campagnaro et al., 2020). Out of these 51, 86% did not pursue dental treatment (Campagnaro et al., 2020). There was an association between fear and parents' willingness to bring their children to dentists. A US survey study also reported that 46.7% of adults postponed their dental visit due to the pandemic (Kranz et al., 2021).

However, it is not clear how US students have perceived the pandemic, and this may change their dental care and decisions to visit dentists. Additionally, the fear level of COVID-19 and cultural background may also impact behavior that is related to dental health. The goal of this study is to close this research gap by examining how the COVID-19 pandemic has affected the eating habits, dental homecare habits, dental visits, and fear levels of US students, and whether family cultural background plays a role in the decision making. This would help to understand more on how COVID-19 impacts oral health.

METHODOLOGY

Aim of the study

The present study explores how the COVID-19 pandemic has affected the dental health among US students, which could be insightful for future health education.

Research Design

This is a cross-sectional study. An anonymous online questionnaire consisted of 22 mandatory questions that targeted sociodemographic variables (age, gender, and cultural background), dietary changes (soft drink, snack, and nutrient supplement consumption), dental homecare (brushing and flossing), dental visits, and fear of COVID-19 (Table 1 Appendix). A pilot study was performed with 20 students to test the questionnaire and clarify questions and answer choices. Prior to submitting the questionnaire, participants had consented to having their answers analyzed in research reports.

Consent and Ethical Issues

All ethical considerations were followed for the current study. Informed consent was taken from respondents during data collection.

Confidentiality and privacy of the respondents were maintained; no data would be disclosed to a third party. No identifiers such as name or pictures were disclosed in the article or while conducting the study. Ethical guidelines of research were followed.

Data Collection Procedure

The target group for this study was US middle and high schoolers aged 10 to 18, mainly from North Carolina. Responses were collected from February to April 2021 through a Google form. The questionnaire was shared through social media (Instagram, WeChat), email, text messaging, and word of mouth. A total of 332 individual responses were received. Responses to 14 questions that are related to dental health were used in this study.

Twenty-three responses were removed due to error entry, nonsensical, and/or missing data. For this study, we defined biannual or annual checkups as routine dental visits. Emergency, trauma, and orthodontic procedures were not counted as routine dental visits. For dental visits prior to the pandemic (DVPP), if the respondent selected “Yes, for regular six-month checkup and dental treatment” and/or indicated annual dentist appointment, then DVPP was coded as 1. If the respondent selected neither of them, then DVPP was set as 0. Similarly, for dental visits during the pandemic (DVDP), if the response included “regular six-month checkup and dental treatment,” indicated annual dentist appointment, or described efforts to make routine dental checkups, then DVDP was coded as 1. Otherwise, DVDP was set as 0, which includes visits for urgent, emergency, and orthodontic care. Family cultural background was defined as US if the respondent has at least one parent with US cultural background versus

non-US if none of the respondent's parents have US cultural background. The overall fear level of COVID-19 was on a 6-point scale from 0-5, with 0 representing "Not afraid at all" and 5 representing "Extremely fearful." Dental homecare was defined as tooth brushing and flossing. If the respondent selected "Less seriously" or "More seriously because of starting orthodontic treatment," then dental care was coded as 0. If the respondent selected "With the same level of seriousness," then dental care was coded as 1. If the respondent selected "More seriously," then dental care was set as 2.

Changes in soft drink, snack, and supplement/vitamin intake were categorized as increased, decreased, or stayed the same. "I do not take vitamin or nutrient supplements" was an additional answer choice for the supplement question for respondents who do not take any supplements. Among the supplement takers, a variable GUMMY was set as 1 for responses including gummy as a supplement form, and 0 for responses with only tablets, liquid, capsule, and/or powder forms.

Statistical Analyses

All statistical analyses were performed using SAS 9.4 (SAS, Cary, NC). The statistics for demographics, fear level of COVID-19, eating habits, dental homecare and dental visits prior to pandemic (DVPP) were compared between the group that kept routine dental visits (DVDPY)

and the group that did not during the pandemic (DVDPN). Wilcoxon two-sample tests were conducted for continuous variables (age and fear level), and the chi-square tests were used for categorical variables (gender; culture; dental care; soft drink, snack, and supplement intake; gummy; and DVPP). A logistic regression model was estimated with dental visits during the pandemic (DVDP) as the dependent variable. The primary analysis was to test if cultural background and fear level of COVID-19 affected the DVDP, adjusted for DVPP, age, and gender. The level of significance was at 0.05 for all statistical analyses.

RESULTS

After data cleaning, a total of 309 subjects were included in this study. Table 2 shows that the mean age was 15.9 years old with more girls (62.8%) and more students with US cultural background (55.3%). The mean fear level was 2.8 with a standard deviation of 1.2. About half of the students (54.7%) increased consumption of snacks, 19.1% decreased, and 26.2% kept the same level of snack consumption compared to prior to the pandemic (Figure 1). About 53.1% of the respondents did not change their consumption of soft drinks, while 16.8% increased, and 30.1% decreased the use of soft drinks during the pandemic (Figure 2). Among all of the respondents, 45.3% of them did not

take any nutrient or vitamin supplements either prior to or during the pandemic. For those who took supplements, 30.7% did not change their supplement intake habits, and 19.1% took increased amounts of supplements (Figure 3). Among the 169 supplement consumers, 60.4% took them in gummy form, and the rest of them used tablet, capsule, liquid, and powder forms (Figure 4). Among the total respondents, 64.7% reported the same level of seriousness of dental care at home during the pandemic, and 21.0% reported less serious dental care compared to prior to the pandemic (Figure 5).

The sample characteristics stratified by DVDP are listed in Table 2 (Appendix). No difference in age and gender between the two stratified groups was observed. Prior to the pandemic, 86.1% of students visited dental offices for regular checkups, and this number significantly dropped to 74.1% during the pandemic ($P < 0.0001$). Compared to the group DVDPN (mean = 3.1), group DVDPY (mean = 2.7) had a significantly lower overall fear level of COVID-19 ($P = 0.009$). Students with US cultural background tended to visit dental offices more during the pandemic (60.7%) than those without US cultural background (40.0%) ($P = 0.001$). Compared to students with non-US cultural background (mean = 2.9), those with US cultural background (mean = 2.6) also had a less overall fear level of COVID-19 (Figure 6, $P = 0.037$). There was no significant change between

the groups DVDPY and DVDPN in home dental care and eating habits, including soft drink, snack, and supplement intake; and gummy supplement.

Table 3 displays the model results of odds ratios (OR), 95% confidence interval, and P values in predicting DVDP by cultural background and fear level of COVID-19, adjusted for age, gender, and DVPP. Students with US cultural background were more likely to visit the dentist during the pandemic (OR = 2.25, 95% CI = [1.22, 4.14], $P = 0.009$). Students with greater overall fear levels tended not to visit the dentist during the pandemic compared to those with less overall fear levels (OR = 0.70, 95% CI = [0.54, 0.24], $P = 0.006$). DVPP was also strongly associated with DVDP (OR, CI, $P < 0.001$), indicating those who visited dentists for regular checkups prior to the pandemic tended to keep the dental visits during the pandemic (OR = 8.74, CI = [4.16, 18.35], $P < 0.0001$), while those who did not have routine dental visits prior to the pandemic were less likely to visit the dentist during the pandemic. Age and gender were not significantly associated with DVDP ($P > 0.06$).

Table 3: Logistic regression model results (Odds Ratios, 95% Confidence Interval and P values) predicting dental visit during pandemic

Variables	OR	95% CI	P
Age (years)	0.804	0.639, 1.012	0.064
Gender (Girls vs. Boys)	1.511	0.819, 2.787	0.186
Culture (US vs. Non-US)	2.25	1.223, 4.137	0.009
Fear Level	0.698	0.541, 0.241	0.006
Dental Visit Prior to Pandemic (Yes vs. No)	8.735	4.157, 18.352	<0.0001

DISCUSSION

Keeping good oral hygiene habits is crucial to maintain dental health. The lockdowns and school closings due to the COVID-19 pandemic have forced millions of students to attend virtual school from home and experience huge lifestyle changes. Children are among the most vulnerable to life changes (Clark et al., 2020). During the COVID-19 pandemic, routine dental visits were observed to decrease significantly; on the other hand, there are more urgent or

emergency visits due to dental infections or caries-related problems, suggesting a negative impact (Eggmann et al., 2021). However, it is not clear how the pandemic has impacted adolescences’ dental health. In this study, we explored and analyzed how the COVID-19 pandemic has impacted US middle and high school students’ eating habits, fear levels of COVID-19, dental homecare, and dental visits.

We found that the COVID-19 pandemic has greatly changed students’ eating habits and dental homecare. More than half of the respondents reported increased snack consumption during the pandemic. This is likely due to increased time staying at home, making access to and eating snacks much easier compared to when students attended school in person. This poses an increased caries risk due to the increased frequency and/or amount of snacks, which can cause a prolonged low pH environment in the oral cavity (Bibby et al., 1986; Lingström&Birkhed, 1993). However, about 30% of respondents had decreased consumption of soft drinks compared to prior to the pandemic. This may be due to fewer social activities or limited/no access to school cafeterias, which are the major providers of soft drinks for students. About 19% had increased supplemental nutrient intake due to the pandemic while 30% remained the same. The increase is likely because respondents tried to boost immunity to prevent or alleviate health

problems during the pandemic. Among all the forms of supplements, gummy form is the most dominant (60.4%). Gummies contain high amounts of sugar, and their soft, sticky texture makes them easily adhere to tooth surfaces for prolonged periods of time, which causes a great risk of caries development (Galo, 2011). Moreover, with increased consumption of both snacks and sugary supplements, nearly 2/3 of students practiced homecare with the same level of seriousness before and during the pandemic. About 20% of respondents had even less serious brushing and flossing, likely due to irregular schedules from virtual school, more screen time, and less sleep time. All of these results indicate that the pandemic has greatly changed the lifestyles of US students and increased their risk for dental caries. Our findings are consistent with other studies (Campagnaro et al., 2020; Sidor&Rzymiski, 2020; Verlinden et al., 2021).

Overall, the students had decreased routine dental checkups during the pandemic (74.1%), compared to about 86.1% prior to the pandemic. This decrease in students is smaller than that of the adult data from a survey, which reported that 46.7% of adults postpone their dental visit due to the pandemic (Kranz et al., 2021). Regression analysis showed that three factors are associated with the decision making regarding dental visits during the pandemic. The first factor is the fear level of COVID-19. More than half of the respondents reported significant fear of

COVID-19 with a mean value of 2.80. Those who chose not to have dental checkups during the pandemic had a significantly higher fear level (mean = 3.1) compared to those who did not (mean = 2.7). This is likely due to being afraid of exposure to other people and/or of cross transmission risks at dental offices. However, to date, there are no confirmed cases of cross-transmission in a dental office setting (Üstün et al., 2021).

The second factor is the respondent's dental visit pattern and history prior to the pandemic. Respondents who had been routinely visiting dentists once or twice a year before the pandemic were more likely to keep their routine dental checkups during the pandemic. Routine dental checkups are essential to maintain good dental care and reflect students' attitudes toward dental health. If a student did not bother to have dental checkups before the pandemic, it would be unlikely that they would make a dental visit during the pandemic -- unless there was an urgent or emergency issue.

The third factor is the family cultural background of the respondent. Interestingly, we found that respondents with at least one parent of US cultural background are more likely to have routine dental checkups during the pandemic compared to respondents whose parents are both of a non-US cultural background. There are few studies on how

cultural background influences people's perception of the COVID-19 pandemic, but different ethnicities showed various reactions to restricted social activities and fear of the pandemic (Bruns et al., 2020). These data demonstrated that respondents with US cultural background have significantly less fear levels (mean = 2.6) than those with non-US cultural background (mean = 2.9), indicating that cultural background may affect the decision-making directly, or indirectly by influencing the fear level. This also implies that dental providers should consider a patient's cultural background in order to make dental care more readily available and accessible for people of different cultures.

CONCLUSION

To our knowledge, this study implied that the COVID-19 pandemic has had an overall negative impact on the dental health of US middle and high school students. In general, students have experienced increased snacking and more sugary supplement intake with the same or less serious level of dental homecare. This poses an increased risk of dental caries. Students who had higher fear levels, did not establish routine dental checkups, and come from a non-US cultural background are more likely not to visit dentists during the pandemic. Lacking routine visits poses another risk of compromised dental health. Altogether, these explain the increased urgent care treatment

needs during the pandemic period (Eggmann et al., 2021).

Our study provided evidence that it is necessary for dental health providers to be more proactive in providing dental health education in diet, homecare, and dental visit guidance during this special time. Dental health providers should also consider cultural differences. In addition, mental health counseling and education to minimize fear level of the pandemic may also be helpful to maintain routine dental health checkups.

LIMITATIONS

There are several limitations of our study. The survey distribution was not random and was only limited to respondents that have contact with the authors. Thus, most samples are within North Carolina. Larger samples need to be analyzed to increase the statistical power. Additionally, it is challenging to clearly categorize the cultural background because families have mixed cultural backgrounds. It is also difficult to determine each parent's influence in family behaviors and decision making. The questionnaire design could have been more simplified to minimize answering confusion. For the fear level of COVID-19 question, we could have adopted the recent published fear scale for COVID-19 (Ahorsu et

al., 2020) or the SARS fear scale (Ho et al., 2005).

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Appendix

Table 1: Survey Questionnaire

Question	Answer options
1. Your present age	
2. Your gender	Male; Female; Other (the respondent could write the answer)
3. The state in which you live:	
4. Which country or countries are your parents from (considering cultural background)?	
5. In general, how many days per WEEK do you go to school IN-PERSON during the Covid-19 pandemic?	0 days (fully virtual); 1 day; 2 days; 3 days; 4 days; 5 days;

- | | |
|--|---|
| 6. Compared to before the Covid-19 pandemic, your current academic learning experience is... | More challenging; Less challenging; Has not changed |
| 7. During the Covid-19 pandemic, how many hours per WEEK on average do you socialize outside of school with peers IN-PERSON (such as sports, clubs, group interactions)? | Less than 30 minutes; 30 minutes to 1 hour; 1-2 hours; 2-3 hours; 3-4 hours; 4-5 hours; More than 5 hours |
| 8. During the Covid-19 pandemic, how many hours per WEEK on average do you socialize outside of school with peers VIRTUALLY (such as texting, video calling, online gaming)? | Less than 30 minutes; 30 minutes to 1 hour; 1-2 hours; 2-3 hours; 3-4 hours; 4-5 hours; More than 5 hours |
| 9. On average, how many hours do you spend on screen DAILY? (including online school) | |
| 10. During the Covid-19 pandemic, how many hours per WEEK on average do you currently have physical activity/exercise (such as sports, walking, biking, gym, etc)? | Less than 30 minutes; 30 minutes to 1 hour; 1-2 hours; 2-3 hours; 3-4 hours; 4-5 hours; More than 5 hours |
| 11. Compared to before the Covid-19 pandemic, your current sleep time and/or quality is... | Better; Worse; The same |

12. Compared to before the Covid-19 pandemic, the time your family spends together with active interactions... Has increased; Has decreased; Has not changed

13. Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by having little interest or pleasure in doing things? Not at all; Several days (no more than seven days); More than half the days (more than seven days); nearly every day

14. Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by feeling down, depressed or hopeless? Not at all; Several days (no more than seven days); More than half the days (more than seven days); nearly every day

15. Compared to before the Covid-19 pandemic, your current consumption of soft drinks, soda, juice, and sparkling beverages... Has increased; Has decreased; Has not changed

16. Compared to before the Covid-19 pandemic, your current snack consumption... Has increased; Has decreased; Has not changed

17. If you take vitamin or nutrient supplements, what form do they come in? (Check all that apply) Tablet/capsule; Gummy; Liquid; Powder; I do not take vitamin or nutrient supplements

18. Compared to before the Covid-19 pandemic, your current consumption of vitamin or nutrient supplements... Has increased; Has decreased; Has not changed; I do not take vitamin or nutrient supplements

<p>19. Were you undergoing dental treatment before the pandemic (check all that apply)?</p>	<p>No; Yes, for regular six-month check up and dental treatment; Yes, for orthodontic treatment; Yes, but only for urgent treatments (toothache or trauma); Other (respondent could write the answer)</p>
<p>20. Would you go to a dental appointment during the pandemic (check all that apply)?</p>	<p>Yes, as usual for regular six-month check up and dental treatment; Yes, for orthodontic treatment; Yes, but only for urgent treatments (toothache or trauma); No, because there is a risk of contracting Covid-19; No, because I don't feel it is necessary; Other (respondent could write the answer)</p>
<p>21. Compared to before the Covid-19 pandemic, you take teeth-brushing and flossing...</p>	<p>More seriously; More seriously because of starting orthodontic treatment; Less seriously; With the same level of seriousness; Other (respondent could write the answer)</p>
<p>22. Overall, your fear of Covid-19 is ...</p>	<p>0 (not afraid at all); 1; 2; 3; 4;5 (Extremely fearful)</p>
<p>23. I consent to the fact that my anonymous answers will be analyzed in a research report.</p>	<p>Yes, I consent</p>

Table 2: Sample characteristics stratified by dental visit during pandemic.

Variable	Total	Dental Visit During Pandemic = No (DVDPN)	Dental Visit During Pandemic = Yes (DVDPY)	P
N	309	80 (25.9%)	229 (74.1%)	< 0.0001
Age	15.9 ± 1.4	15.9±1.2	15.9 ± 1.4	0.964
Girls	194 (62.8%)	47 (58.8%)	147 (64.2%)	0.386
US	171 (55.3%)	32 (40.0%)	139 (60.7%)	0.001
Fear	2.8 ± 1.2	3.1 ± 1.2	2.7 ± 1.2	0.009
Dental Care	Less seriously 65 (21.0%)	18 (22.5%)	47 (20.5%)	0.374
	Same level of seriousness 200 (64.7%)	53 (66.3%)	147 (64.2%)	
	More seriously 44 (14.2%)	9 (11.2%)	35 (15.3%)	
Soft Drinks	Has decreased 93 (30.1%)	23 (28.8%)	70 (30.6%)	0.219
	Has increased 52 (16.8%)	48 (60.0%)	116 (50.7%)	
	Has not changed 164 (53.1%)	9 (11.2%)	43 (18.8%)	
Snacks	Has decreased 59 (19.1%)	15 (18.8%)	44 (19.2%)	0.955
	Has increased 169 (54.7%)	22 (27.5%)	59 (25.8%)	
	Has not changed 81 (26.2%)	43 (53.7%)	126 (55.0%)	
Supplement Intake	Has decreased 15 (4.9%)	5 (6.2%)	10 (4.4%)	0.842
	Has increased 59 (19.1%)	14 (17.5%)	45 (19.7%)	
	Has not changed 95 (30.7%)	23 (28.8%)	72 (31.4%)	
	Do not take supplements 140 (45.3%)	38 (47.5%)	102 (44.5%)	
Gum	Yes 102 (60.4%)	26 (61.9%)	76 (59.8%)	0.813
Among Supplement Intakers	No 67 (39.6%)	16 (38.1%)	51 (40.2%)	
Dental Visit Before	Yes 266 (86.1%)	52 (65.0%)	214 (93.5%)	<0.0001

Pande mic	No	43 (13.9%)	28 (35.0%)	15 (6.5%)
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